

Equitable Data Valuation for Semantic Segmentation

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Abstract

In this study, the Shapley value is used to evaluate training data for challenging supervised learning tasks, particularly semantic segmentation. The Shapley value, originating from cooperative game theory is appealing as it satisfies the set of properties required by a data value notion. But, the Shapley value suffers from exponential complexity compute time. Among the approximation algorithms for the Shapley value, the approximation using the K-nearest neighbor (KNN) classifier, called KNN Shapley, is the most efficient as it requires training the model only once while the other approximation algorithms require training the model multiple times. We propose a modification to the KNN Shapley value, to apply to semantic segmentation tasks, providing a measure to determine the quality of data to train semantic segmentation algorithms. We evaluate the values produced by KNN Shapley algorithm in the label noise correction scenario and see that the values produced by the modified algorithm can detect noisy labels.

1 Introduction

Recent studies show that building artificial intelligence systems based on data over or in addition to the training algorithm can lead to substantial improvement in its performance[1]. Leveraging data and building data-centric systems has enabled advancements in various applications such as autonomous driving and healthcare. But, there is a lack of standardized measures to determine the quality of data and attribute the contribution of the data to their corresponding sources. Consequently, the data valuation problem has gained increasing traction in the research community. So far, approaches for valuating the data when the data is used for simpler supervised learning tasks such as classification have been proposed. But, there has yet to be a way to value the data when the data is used for more complex supervised learning tasks such as semantic segmentation. In this work, we propose a data value notion when the data is used for semantic segmentation.

The Shapley value originating from cooperative game theory has been proposed to value data[2][3]. It defines a way to distribute total gains contributed by each player in a set of players. The supervised learning task can be formulated as a cooperative game between different training data points and the Shapley value can be used to value the data points to determine the contribution of each data point towards the overall performance of the training algorithm on the supervised learning task. The Shapley value is interesting because it possesses desirable properties for a data value notion like fairness and additivity of values in multiple data uses.

A key drawback of Data Shapley is that it determines the marginal contribution of a point to every possible subset of training data and averages the marginal contribution over all subsets, leading to a very expensive exponential complexity. Using the exact Shapley is intractable for neural networks, typically used for semantic segmentation. Recent works by Ghorbani and Zhou[3] have been focusing on improving the computing time of the Shapley value for large training datasets, by computing an approximation of the exact Shapley value. Monte-Carlo and Gradient-based Shapley value approximations have been proposed to improve the computing time of the Shapley value. But, these approximations require training the ML model multiple times and are still intractable for large training datasets and complex models like neural networks. To solve this problem, an approximation of the Shapley value for data valuation based on the K-nearest neighbor classifier, viz., KNN-Shapley[4] has been introduced that requires training the ML model only once and scales quasi-linearly with the training data size, linearly with the validation data size and independent of the model size. The key idea is to approximate the model by a K-nearest neighbor classifier which

allows for reduction of the number of subsets to be examined for computing the Shapley value by leveraging its locality structure, providing significant efficiency improvement.

While the KNN-Shapley algorithm has shown to value data efficiently for data used in supervised learning tasks like classification, it cannot be used directly for more complex supervised learning tasks like Semantic Segmentation, due to the usage of masks as the labels. We propose a modification to the KNN-Shapley algorithm that allows valuating data when used for semantic segmentation tasks. We apply it to the various label noise scenarios pertaining to semantic segmentation and show that the modified KNN-Shapley measure captures the noisy labels effectively while still preserving the efficiency and scalability of the original KNN-Shapley algorithm.

2 KNN Shapley

2.1 The Shapley Value

The Shapley value originating from cooperative game theory distributes the total gains by each player in a set of players. The supervised learning problem can be formulated as a cooperative game of players where each training data point is a player contributing to the learning of the algorithm for the supervised learning task.

Given a performance measure U , the Shapley value for training data z_i is defined as the average marginal contribution of z_i to all possible subsets of D formed by other training points:

$$v_{\text{shap}}(z_i) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{S \subseteq D \setminus \{z_i\}} \frac{1}{\binom{N-1}{|S|}} [U(S \cup \{z_i\}) - U(S)]$$

The Shapley value is desired because it satisfies the following properties:

1. Group rationality: The performance of a machine learning model includes a contribution by all training points, i.e., $U(D) = \sum_{z_i \in D} v(z_i)$.
2. Fairness: (1) Two data points contributing the same amount to the performance of the model need to have the same value. That is, if for data z_i and z_j and any subset $S \subseteq D \setminus \{z_i, z_j\}$, we have $U(S \cup \{i\}) = U(S \cup \{j\})$, then $v(z_i) = v(z_j)$. (2) Data points that do not contribute to the performance of the model need to be assigned a value of 0, i.e., $v(z_i) = 0$ if $U(S \cup \{z_i\}) = 0$ for all $S \subseteq D \setminus z_i$.
3. Additivity: When the overall performance measure is the sum of separate performance measures, the overall value of a training data point should be the sum of its value under each performance measure $v(z_i, U_1) + v(z_i, U_2) = v(z_i, U_1 + U_2)$ for $z_i \in D$.

While the Shapley value has the above desirable properties of a data value notion, computing it is very expensive. Evaluating the exact Shapley value requires computing the marginal contribution of each training point to all possible subsets, which is $O(2^N)$. Such complexity is clearly impractical for valuating a large number of training points. This complexity is infeasible for simpler machine learning models, let alone models used for semantic segmentation.

Ghorbani and Zou[3] proposed two Monte Carlo-based approaches to approximating the Shapley value. The central idea behind these approaches is to treat a training point's Shapley value as its expected contribution to a random subset and use sample average to approximate the expectation. However, these Monte Carlo-based approaches cannot circumvent the need to re-train models and therefore are not viable for large models used in semantic segmentation.

2.2 KNN-Shapley

To circumvent the need to retrain the models, Jia et al[4] introduced the KNN-based Shapley value, which involves approximating the model with a KNN classifier leveraging its efficiency and locality structure.

Given a single validation point x_{val} with the label y_{val} , the KNN classifier determines the top-K training points $(x_{\alpha_1}, \dots, x_{\alpha_K})$ most similar to x_{val} and assigns the probability of $x_{0=\text{val}}$ taking the

label y_{val} as $P[x_{val} \rightarrow y_{val}] = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K \mathbb{1}[y_{\alpha_i} = y_{val}]$. In particular, it recursively assigns the Shapley values for each training data point as follows[5]:

$$v(z_{\alpha_N}) = \frac{\mathbb{1}[y_{\alpha_N} = y_{val}]}{N}$$

$$v(z_{\alpha_i}) = v(z_{\alpha_{i+1}}) + \frac{\mathbb{1}[y_{\alpha_i} = y_{val}] - \mathbb{1}[y_{\alpha_{i+1}} = y_{val}]}{K} \frac{\min\{K, i\}}{i}$$

The above can be readily extended to validation data points as well. KNN Shapley provides an efficient way to compute the approximate Shapley, requiring only $O(N \log N)$ time for each validation data point. The intuition for achieving such exponential improvement is that for KNN, the marginal contribution $U(S \cup z_i) - U(S)$ only depends on the relative distance of z_i and K-nearest neighbors in S to the validation point. When calculating the Shapley value, instead of considering all $S \subseteq D \setminus \{z_i\}$, we only need to focus on the subsets that result in distinctive K-nearest neighbors.

Jia et al[4] proposed the following algorithm to value the training data importance for deep neural networks:

1. Given the training set, train the network and obtain the deep features (i.e., the input to the last softmax layer);
2. Train a KNN classifier on the deep features and corresponding labels and further calibrate K such that the resulting KNN mimics the performance of the original deep net.
3. With a proper choice of K obtained from the last step, use the KNN Shapley value assignment to compute the Shapley value of the deep features.

For other models, the algorithm computes the KNN Shapley value on the raw data. The complexity of the above algorithm is $O(Nd + N \log N)$ where d is the dimension of deep feature representation. Unlike the monte-carlo based methods introduced by Ghorbani and Zhou[3], the above algorithm does not require retraining models. It should be noted that the data values produced by this algorithm seek to distribute the overall yield of a cooperative game across deep features rather than raw data. Jia et al show that these values can still reflect data usefulness.

3 KNN Shapley for Semantic Segmentation

While the KNN-Shapley algorithm is shown to work for tasks like classification it is not shown that the algorithm can be applied to complex tasks like semantic segmentation. It is to be noted that the major difference between classification and segmentation is the difference in the label. In classification, we have a singular scalar value, whereas in segmentation we have a 2D matrix or image called the mask. Due to this difference, the Shapley value assignment proposed by Jia et al[4] fails to work in the case of image segmentation. Given a performance measure for segmentation U , we propose the following modification to the KNN Shapley value assignment[5] for valuing training data when used for training semantic segmentation models.

$$v(z_{\alpha_N}) = \frac{U(y_{\alpha_N}, y_{val})}{N}$$

$$v(z_{\alpha_i}) = v(z_{\alpha_{i+1}}) + \frac{U(y_{\alpha_i}, y_{val}) - U(y_{\alpha_{i+1}}, y_{val})}{K} \frac{\min\{K, i\}}{i}$$

where U can be typical performance measure used in semantic segmentation such as the intersection over union (IoU). The motivation for this modification was that computing KNN Shapley values for classification tasks require a comparison between the labels of the nearest neighbors from the training set to the label of the validation data point. Since the labels for semantic segmentation are masks, there is no straightforward way to make this comparison. By computing the performance measure like the intersection over union, between the predicted masks for the nearest training set instances to the validation data point, and the predicted mask for the validation data point, it can provide a similar comparison between said labels. It is to be noted that the comparison would be a value between 0 and 1 with values closer to 1 indicating higher similarity and values

closer to 0 indicating lower similarity. In our experiments, we find that the above modification provides the same desirable properties required by a data value notion, and does not require retraining models.

4 Experiments

In this section, we validate our approach by running the modified KNN Shapley algorithm on label noise scenarios in two semantic segmentation settings, viz., semantic segmentation of cats and dogs, and semantic segmentation of cells in histology images.

Labels in the real world are often inaccurate due to factors such as automatic labeling, inexperienced labeling, or label tampering by malicious actors attempting to poison the data. While human experts can identify mislabeled samples, checking all labels manually for large training datasets is not practical. To address this issue, the concept of a data value can be used to help human specialists prioritize the verification process and focus on the cases most likely to be affected. Specifically, the data points with the lowest data values need to be prioritized and ranked accordingly.

Simulating label noise scenarios in classification tasks involves flipping the label of a percentage of the instances from the training dataset. There arises a question of how to simulate similar label noise scenarios for semantic segmentation. Label noise is generally introduced in semantic segmentation scenarios when the annotated mask does not correctly encompass the object, i.e., the mask may exclude portions of the object or include some of the object’s background. To simulate such a label noise scenario, we randomly dilate and erode a ratio of the ground truth masks of a subset of the Oxford-IIIT pets dataset[6] consisting of only cats and dogs. The ratio we chose was 20% and we used a 5x5 kernel and 5 iterations for dilation and erosion. To extract deep features which are the input to the K-Nearest Neighbor algorithm used in KNN-Shapley, we trained a UNet[7] model with ResNet50[8] and EfficientNetB3[9] backbones for 50 epochs on the noisy data. The UNet with the EfficientNetB3 backbones provided better segmentations with richer deep features. The value of K was set to 10. Following Ghorbani and Zou[3], we ran this modified KNN Shapley algorithm with this setting and the detection performance of the algorithm in comparison with random assignment is illustrated in 1. We can see that the detection performance of the KNN Shapley algorithm significantly outperforms the random baseline.

Figure 1: KNN Shapley applied to the Cats/Dogs Segmentation setting

An important use case of semantic segmentation is the segmentation of nuclei in Hematoxylin Eosin stained histology images. In fact, it is a fundamental prerequisite in the digital pathology

workflow. Unfortunately, it is quite common to see noisy labels in the datasets used to train the algorithms that segment these nuclei. The most common label noise scenario is that not all cell nuclei within a region are annotated. To simulate such a scenario, we randomly removed 40% of the cells in 20% of the masks from the CoNSeP dataset. Using the same UNet with an EfficientNetB3 architecture trained for 50 epochs, the modified KNN Shapley algorithm was run on the deep features. The detection performance of the algorithm is shown in Figure 2. Again, we see that the detection performance of the KNN Shapley algorithm performs better than the random baseline.

Figure 2: KNN Shapley applied to the Nuclei Segmentation setting

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we propose a modification to the efficient heuristic to approximate the Shapley value based on KNN proxies (KNN Shapley) to adapt to semantic segmentation use cases. We show the utility of our approach to two different semantic segmentation settings: segmentation of cats and dogs, and segmentation of nuclei in histology images, while still having the same efficiency and scalability of KNN Shapley when applied to classification.

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